

Study of Lead Acid Batteries in Photovoltaic Systems

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Abstract

Battery is a crucial component in a photovoltaic system. It provides energy for the loads during night or non sunny days. It can be considered as a stabilizer. Most of the batteries used in photovoltaic systems nowadays are lead acid batteries. The study of a photovoltaic system necessitates in a first time equivalent models of the main components such as photovoltaic generator model, storage element. The knowledge of their electrical characteristics remains a key factor in the simulation analysis. The battery behavior has been largely described in the literature by many authors. Most of the models require the knowledge of appropriate parameters. Batteries remain a complicated element, since they are the only dynamic element in a photovoltaic system. In fact many events can occur such as charge and discharge. Many parameters vary during the processes of voltage, current, density, temperature and resistivity. The CIEMAT model is general and normalized with battery capacity, it necessitate few input parameters. It takes into account the discharge, the charge and the overcharge processes and it can be applied for wide range of lead acid batteries used in photovoltaic systems. The CIEMAT model presents a good performance to represent dynamic and complex battery operation. This paper reviews the general lead acid batteries model and it agreement with experimental data obtained from tests with in photovoltaic systems.

Keywords: Photovoltaic System, Resistivity, Voltage, Electrical Characteristics.

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